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Use of agile methods in the education of engineering students

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INTRODUCTION

In this paper, first we present the project management methodology SCRUM as it is generally used in enterprise projects. Then we propose an adaptation of this technique to the context of education: we will call it SCRUM educational management.

Such an approach was applied during a series of classes in an engineering school. Its results - in terms of behavioural skills acquisition (soft skills) - are then presented together with some hindsight based on the feedback collected from this pedagogical experiment.

At the origin of the experiment, two premises: future engineers must acquire the necessary soft skills during their education and students are in need of a constant and enjoyable renewal of learning rhythms; with such context and its widespread use in the corporate world, SCRUM seemed like a good fit for its application in engineers' education.

In France, the accreditation agency for engineering education (Commission des titres d'Ingénieurs) insists on the fact that humanities and technical education must be integrated. The fact that a method used in software companies can be used for education of engineers is one example of this integration.

1 SCRUM PROJECT MANAGEMENT

1.1 Agility

SCRUM processes are currently widely adopted in private companies interested in so-called *agile* management. Agility advocates deploying a project management process based on the reactivity (capacity of adaptation in situations of change) of the actors of the project in favour of the final user (the client) of the envisioned product or service. It contrasts with a more classical approach to project management (relying on specification gathered up front and frozen at project start) in that it allows for a more flexible list of requirements that evolves and matures as the project progresses and new input from the client appears (his feedback, in an agile project, is very often required).

This methodology aims both at taking into account complex situations and at better satisfying final consumer. More information can be found in [1] and for a benchmark of agility among managerial trends see [2].

Agility is particularly interesting in the education of engineers because it forces to build bridges between hard and soft skills: when dealing with a complex project, it is necessary to adapt and student's skills will have to switch back and forth from technical ones to those more linked with personal development such team spirit, organizational capacity, empathy, good relations with the group.

1.2 SCRUM

SCRUM [3] is one specific method of agile management centred on the satisfaction of the end-user. It therefore relies heavily on constant collaboration with the customer as well as adaptation to evolving reorientations that this collaboration implies, this is realised through iterative steps that mark out the project management:

- a collaborative estimation (*Planning Poker*) in which self-organizing teams estimate the effort needed to complete tasks and subtasks

- sprints*: time-boxed work periods during which committed tasks are completed

- sprint reviews* and retrospectives during which the team can reflect upon the previous iteration in order to improve its process and obtain customer feedback about the features

- iterations allow a series of advances thanks to series of tests, till the complete satisfaction of end user

In SCRUM teams, some members play a specific role, such as the *Scrum Master* who is the facilitator of the group or of the project team, or the *Product Owner* who is in charge of the more precise definition of the needs of the final customer.

The word "scrum" comes from rugby, where many other metaphors come from in the methodology. For instance, during a scrum (at the end of a sprint), the ball is put back at the centre of the field and can, because of the scrum (interactions between the team and the client), start moving again in a completely different direction that was not initially planned and so reorient the remaining game [4].

The idea of precise timing (time-boxing) of the different phases of the project is closely related to SCRUM, so not only is there a start time and an end time - as in a classically-managed project with the traditional deadline – but also a series of intermediate milestones that split the

project in sprints whose end is a deadline with a debriefing necessary for going to the next step.

The final deadline can or cannot stay the same, but it is preceded of several intermediate deadlines that are decisive for the orientation of the project.

2 A PEDAGOGIC SCRUM

To beneficiate from the advantages of SCRUM method (group cohesion, adaptation to changes, customer orientation) while responding to educational aims, a pedagogic adaptation of SCRUM method was proposed to students.

2.1 Pedagogic objectives

The aim of the module concerning communication practical works (for first year undergraduate students) was to review several methods used for professional and scientific communication as well in oral form as in written ones:

realize a pitch for interpersonal presentation (to present a friend so as to value him),

realize a Curriculum Vitae,

analyse and reproduce specialised stylistic elements (such as an industrial patent or medicine instructions).

The duration of the module was of 7 sessions each of one being one hour and a quarter duration.

These very practical objectives had the aim to introduce some elementary soft skills for these new engineering students.

2.2 Pedagogic sprints

The usual duration of a sprint of SCRUM is between one and four weeks. Because of the specific format of the pedagogic sequence, it was necessary to reduce sprint duration, thanks to a specific time management called the Pomodoro technique [5]. It lays on a time splitting allowing maximal concentration on a short duration (25 minutes).

So, the duration of a pedagogic sprint was fixed to 25 minutes, during this time, students have to realise a predefined task of the project. A stopwatch was displayed on the screen for each sprint so that the student knows the time registration and can check time remaining for the task. During a practical work in Polytech, which is 75 minutes, it was possible to obtain 2 or 3 sprints leading to practical realisation of 2 or 3 activities linked to the project. On the global pedagogic module, it was then possible to realise between 14 to 21 sprints.

2.3 Team Building

The composition of project teams, depending on work atmosphere of practical works, was either free or defined by the teacher, we must precise that in a real SCRUM, this composition is realised after team building operations that aim to identify specific skills of team members to employ them at their best.

The teams of students were of 4 to 5 members and if the teacher had defined the groups he had used the knowledge of the skills he had detected previously.

For the realisation of the task assigned, students can use Internet and could access a specific digital work environment dedicated to this activity which had been filled previously by the teacher with useful documents in link with the sprint to be fulfilled.

2.4 Frame of the module

The module was composed in the following way:

- first session: presentation of the SCRUM method and of the expected results of the module
- second session: sprint 1 professional presentation of a group fellow with a deliverable which is a pitch of 3-minute duration
- third session: sprint 2 realisation of a Curriculum Vitae allowing to get a seasonal employment with a deliverable which is a one-page CV
- fourth session: sprint 3 description of the stylistic device of a scientific text (medicine instructions) with a deliverable which is a list of stylistic remarks
- fifth session: an examination in the pursuit of sprint 3 takes place, here the deliverable is the supervised limited time exam
- sixth session: sprint 4 understanding of an industrial patent text with a deliverable which is the description of the concepts underlying the frame of this text
- seventh session: debriefing of the whole module

For each of the sessions, the teacher is the customer (product owner); he has his own requirements and he asks to each project team to answer them in a definite time and to produce a precise deliverable. Teams of students self-organize during a quick brief, a supervisor for the group can emerge then he is the SCRUM master, if not the teacher acting as supervisor facilitates from time to time the group, he can also reorient it if it stagnates.

At the end of each sprint a debriefing of the sprint is organised with several different conclusions according to what happened previously:

- one of the project team (3 or 4 teams work in parallel) realises a deliverable corresponding to the expectations of the product owner (the teacher), then, all the teams can go to the next sprint after analysis of this deliverable.
- no project team realize a deliverable corresponding to the expectations of the teacher (this case is the more frequently met), then students together with teacher analyse the lacks, and the project is reoriented within a shorter sprint (15 minutes) so as to rectify the deliverable and then conclude the activity step to go to the following one
- all the project teams have realised, sooner than expected, the deliverable wished by the teacher: the product owner gives then a complementary instruction that extends the initial deliverable (for example if the deliverable is a CV, a more specific CV is asked, dedicated for the research of a job in a laboratory in a very precise structure with specific characteristics, this obliges the students to modify the CV to be more fitted to the new strict scenario)

Before going to next sprint, the teacher makes a synthesis of the new skills developed by the students; these new skills are the functionalities implemented in the classical SCRUM method: they are indicators of the project progresses and enlighten its degree of achievement.

At the end of the module, the teacher can also organise a SCRUM of SCRUM: in a meta sprint dedicated to the synthesis of all the newly acquired skills for the session, a deliverable which is a list explicating all these new skills.

3 ANALYSIS OF THE ACTIVITY

3.1 Skills acquired during the process

The students gain the classical hard part of soft skills usually afforded by this module that are: realise a pitch, build a CV, analyse a scientific text, but the use of SCRUM gives them more skills, we have identified them because we were able to observe students; these are:

- ability to solve complex problems
- creativity
- group work: sense of community
- empathy, sense of relational and group communication, team negotiation, team spirit
- ability to manage its own time and organisational skills

These soft skills have been acquired in situation, in link with the expectation of an external customer of which student did not have the time to study the profile and in the frame of an active learning in a very limited time. The pressure generated by a strict timing gives a fun aspect to this activity, as well as the freedom let to the team to organise itself, allows a large exploration of heuristics. Many different solutions are proposed at the end of a sprint and as several groups work in parallel, the debriefing allows a debate on those different solutions, allowing a choice between the different approaches. This final debriefing also allows acquisition on new skills laying on the ability to find the good choice of heuristics.

3.2 Assessments

The fact that the complete module is decomposed into several sprints allows to organise regularly assessment phases, those assessments can be realised on the deliverables because each sprint correspond to a deliverable, so it is possible to evaluate the project team on this deliverable.

For our experience, as many teams did not reach in time the deliverable, other ways of evaluation were chosen: one for the oral part of the initial pitch, the other one is a written evaluation on scientific stylistic. But in each of those cases, assessment criteria have been defined and negotiated with project teams during the sprint before the assessment as in the dialogue between engineers and product owner. This is a realistic way of assessment witch both respects the constraints of our HEI and the real life situation.

3.3 Gamification

The fun aspect of the exercise has really stimulated the students and this nearly "caricatured" way of splitting activities that is also encountered in Marshmallow Challenge [6]

or serious games seems really fitted to engineers education. It is an educational act which is not harmless because it is based on a permanent change ideology which is the one of real life: "Change remains the driving force of agility" [7]. Gamification is very used in active pedagogies and reveals to be a good strategy especially for undergraduate students. However, there could be, as for each pedagogy, students that are reluctant, but as pedagogies are different during the 5 years engineering studies the skills could be obtained latter by another method.

3.4 Improvement suggestions

Several improvements could be brought to this pedagogic SCRUM sequence.

As this method is very much used by computer science engineers, using an electronic planning is something that has much sense, furthermore electronic planning is very convenient to present the splitting of SCRUM activities, the objectives, milestones, realized items or elements to be acquired for each project team. This electronic planning could also be a good backlog for each team

Before the real beginning of the module, it could be interesting to have a more important phase for team building with skill assessments between students. This could give more efficient teams.

Merging the team backlog and the sprint memo: the entirety could "a posteriori" become a lesson that the student can keep.

There is a real need to make a link between pedagogic SCRUM and corporate SCRUM. This could easily be done because this method is really very much used in companies; in France people from companies must intervene at least for 25% in the education of engineers, so it would be easy to find an engineer able to speak about its job. Concerning the education of the teachers realising the course it could also be a real mutual enrichment.

Can a sprint of 2 weeks be compared to a concentrated effort of 25 minutes? We think so thanks to the micro sprints concerning the subjects treated in this module, this could be more difficult on more technical subjects.

CONCLUSION

This paper presents an experimentation realised with engineering students, it is not very frequent that a method currently used in companies be applied for pedagogic aims.

Even if the pedagogic SCRUM is not exactly the same a SCRUM used in companies because of constraints of time or of the necessity of assessments, the major elements of an agile method have been kept.

Specific soft skills can be developed thanks to SCRUM such as the ability to adapt to changing constraint, the respect of time that are those of real life in companies. Soft skills usually developed through classical pedagogy by project can also be the result of this experimentation.

It is important to notice that this experimentation, led with a professional tool, has been conducted by a non-technical teacher on subjects considered by technical teachers as collaterals. This show the necessary transdisciplinary skills of teachers to educate students on transdisciplinary fields.

The adaptation of SCRUM for pedagogy on a small size model with different purposes than those of companies has needed crutches such as the mix of SCRUM and Pomodoro (also used in companies) for the timekeeping of activities: activities become micro-sprints that can be organised during practical works and are more fitted with temporality of young people [8].

This sequence could take advantage of the presentation of real SCRUM by an engineers giving to students another ability which is to project themselves in real life after having played.

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